

CREEP BEHAVIOR OF HIGH-TEMPERATURE COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

In this study the creep behavior of IM7/5250-4 is investigated over a range of temperatures. Short-term creep tests are conducted on $[90]_{8T}$ and $[\pm 45]_{2S}$ laminates to determine transverse and shear creep compliances, respectively. The time-temperature-stress superposition principle is then used in conjunction with explicit shift factors to construct a master creep curve for $S_{66}(t)$ which is validated with long-term experimental data. The creep behavior of multidirectional laminates is also predicted by calculating $E_L(t)$ using laminated plate theory and the ply creep properties, and utilizing this to determine creep strain. These predictions compare favorably with experimental creep data.

INTRODUCTION

The viscoelastic nature of fiber-reinforced plastics provides a unique challenge to the design of structural components with these materials in that the long-term viscoelastic response to mechanical loading in thermal and/or humid environments must be taken into account. This viscoelastic response, or creep, which increases with increasing temperature and absorbed moisture can lead to a decrease in component stiffness, unacceptably large deformations over the life of the structure and, eventually, creep rupture. Because of the relatively low service temperatures of polymeric composites in most structural applications, however, their behavior under creep loading has not been given much attention. As the application of composites is expanded to higher-temperature environments, the ability to predict the time-dependent response of these materials becomes even more critical. The next generation of supersonic transport is anticipated to have a useful life of 60,000 hours, 75 percent of which will be at supersonic speeds and hence high temperature. For example, an aircraft flying at Mach 2.0 or Mach 2.4 will have upper skin temperatures of approximately 125°C and 175°C, respectively. This requires a departure from conventional aerospace-grade epoxy composites to relatively higher-temperature imide-based composites. The airframe material must be able to maintain its structural properties at the application temperature for the necessary length of time; under these conditions, however, composite creep can play a significant role in determining structural performance. There is little documentation in the technical literature on the time-dependent behavior and creep rupture of high-temperature composites.

Design against creep deformation generally requires collecting data over long periods of time which is both costly and impractical, and an accelerated characterization procedure is needed. A number of different procedures have been used in the past to predict the long-term creep response of composite materials including the Time-Temperature-Stress Superposition Principle (TTSSP) [1-3]. This procedure is based on the fact that creep deformation curves for different thermomechanical conditions are of the same shape. Furthermore, an increase in temperature or stress will shift the creep deformation curves to the left on a (logarithmic) time scale, since these conditions accelerate creep. Hence by collecting short-term creep data at elevated temperatures or stresses and shifting them to the left to form one smooth master curve, the long-term creep behavior at lower temperatures or stresses can be predicted. Using this procedure master curves

have been generated for a variety of composite materials. In this work the in-plane viscoelastic response of a high-temperature composite is characterized by short-term creep tests, and these data are used to predict the long-term creep behavior of multidirectional laminates especially at elevated temperatures. The material system chosen is a carbon fiber-reinforced toughened bismaleimide, IM7/5250-4, a candidate for the next generation of military and civilian supersonic transport.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

The material system used in this study is a carbon fiber-reinforced bismaleimide, IM7/5250-4, obtained from Cytek, Inc. as untape prepreg. Laminates with $[90]_{8T}$, $[\pm 45]_{2S}$, $[45/90_2/-45]_S$ and $[45/0/-45/90]_S$ ply orientations were cured in an autoclave with the manufacturer's recommended cure cycle and postcured in an oven at 227°C for six hours for the creep studies. Material properties were also characterized with additional laminate orientations. Rectangular coupons, 2.54 cm x 15.24 cm, were sectioned from the panels described above and instrumented with WK-series 350Ω strain gages from Micro-Measurements, Inc. in the axial direction. In addition transverse strain gages were mounted on the $[\pm 45]_{2S}$ specimens for determination of shear strain. All gages were bonded with M-Bond 610, a high-temperature adhesive, which was cured at 163°C for 4 hours. A dummy specimen containing the same strain gage arrangement was used in elevated temperature tests to compensate for any temperature fluctuations. Glass-epoxy end-tabs were bonded to the grip faces of the test fixture with a high-temperature epoxy adhesive (FM-400), and specimens were gripped directly for the test.

Creep testing was conducted in an air-circulating oven mounted on an MTS test machine. A specimen was allowed to equilibrate at the test temperature before being instantly loaded to the desired creep stress and maintained under constant load for a predetermined period of time. The stresses selected for determination of transverse and shear creep compliances were 40% of the corresponding ultimate specimen strengths at room temperature. The test machine was operated under load control which ensured minimum fluctuation in the applied load. Load and strain were continuously recorded as functions of time on an X-Y recorder for the first 10 minutes and then periodically at 10-minute intervals. A specimen was initially tested at room temperature. After release of the load and complete recovery of the creep strain, the same specimen was then tested at the next higher test temperature. This procedure was repeated for all test temperatures in this study. The test temperature and time and the stress level employed for each laminate orientation are shown in Table 1.

TABLE 1. Test Matrix for Creep Study

Laminate	Creep Stress (MPa)	Creep Time	TEMPERATURE (°C)						
			0	25	50	75	100	125	150
[90] _{8T}	20.4	100 min	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
		22 days				x			
[±45] _{2S}	69.5	100 min	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
		22 days				x			
[45/90 ₂ /-45] _S	51.7	18 h				x			
	103.4	18 h						x	
[45/0/-45/90] _S	206.9	18 h				x		x	

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

PREDICTION OF LONG-TERM CREEP

The material properties characterized in this study are shown in Table 2. Representative stress-strain curves are also displayed in Figure 1. Both longitudinal and transverse tensile stress-strain curves are linear, implying that E_{11} and $E_{22}(0)$ are independent of applied stress. The short-term (100-minute) transverse creep strains from $[90]_{8T}$ specimens and shear creep strains from $[\pm 45]_{2S}$ specimens are shown in Figure 2. At the stresses applied the transverse creep strains are an order of magnitude lower than the shear creep strains and the error in their measurement is consequently greater. For the sake of clarity transverse creep strains at all test temperatures are not displayed in Fig. 2A. From these plots it is evident that both the transverse and shear creep compliances, $S_{22}(t)$ and $S_{66}(t)$, increase with temperature and time.

TABLE 2. Physical and Room Temperature Mechanical Properties of IM7/5250-4

TEST	PROPERTY	VALUE
0° Tension	Modulus, E_{11} (GPa)	166
	Strength (MPa)	2700 ± 180
	Poisson's ratio	0.32
90° Tension	Modulus, $E_{22}(0)$ (GPa)	10
	Strength (MPa)	51.2 ± 4.8
In-Plane Shear	Modulus, $G_{12}(0)$ (GPa)	5.8
	Strength (MPa)	87.8 ± 1.5
Acid Digestion	Fiber volume (%)	60.3
DMA	Glass transition temp. (°C)	245

The time-temperature-stress superposition principle has been used to predict the long-term creep behavior of graphite/epoxy [4] and glass/polyester [3] composites, among others, from short-term creep tests. Yen and Williamson [5] developed analytical expressions, based on a creep power law referred to as the Findley equation [6], for the horizontal and vertical shift factors required for such an accelerated characterization procedure. For a unidirectional stress the Findley equation can be expressed as:

$$\epsilon = \epsilon_0 + mt^n$$

where ϵ is the creep strain, ϵ_0 is the instantaneous strain and t is the time. For a specific thermomechanical condition this expression becomes

$$\epsilon(\sigma, T, t) = \epsilon_0(\sigma, T) + m(\sigma, T)t^n$$

where T is the temperature and σ is the applied stress. Based on the TTSSP, this creep strain $\epsilon(\sigma, T, t)$ can be expressed in terms of the creep response at a given reference condition (σ_0, T_0) through analytically-derived shift factors. The power law described above, however, does not provide a good fit to the creep data in Fig. 2 in spite of its wide applicability for a number of viscoelastic materials. Instead, the best fit to the data is provided by a logarithmic expression

$$\epsilon = \epsilon_0 + m \log(t)$$

which for a particular thermomechanical condition (σ, T) becomes

FIGURE 1. Typical stress-strain curves for IM7/5250-4 in axial and transverse tension and in-plane shear.

FIGURE 2. Creep response of (A) a [90]_{8T} laminate and (B) a [±45]_{2S} laminate of IM7/5250-4 over the temperature range 0-150°C.

$$\epsilon(\sigma, T, t) = \epsilon_0(\sigma, T) + m(\sigma, T) \log(t)$$

This expression was found to provide a good fit to the creep data of four plastic laminates in an earlier study [7] for creep times out to 2000 hours.

Using the accelerated characterization procedure and shift factors derived from the logarithmic expression above, a master curve was generated for the shear creep strains at a reference condition of 75°C and 69.5 MPa and is shown in Figure 3 on a semi-logarithmic plot. Three creep strains from long-term (22-day) creep tests conducted under the reference conditions are also shown on this plot and appear to follow the master curve. A similar master curve can be

derived for the transverse creep strain. It appears, therefore, that the accelerated characterization procedure used in conjunction with analytical expressions for the shift factors allows a fairly accurate prediction of long-term creep (out to approximately 22 days in Fig. 3) from short-term (100-minute) creep tests.

FIGURE 3. Master curve for the creep shear strain of IM7/5250-4 at 75°C and 69.5 MPa.

FIGURE 4. Variation of instantaneous transverse and in-plane shear moduli of IM7/5250-4 with temperature.

CREEP PREDICTION FOR MULTIDIRECTIONAL LAMINATES

An attempt was made to predict the creep behavior of $[45/90_2/-45]_S$ and $[45/0/-45/90]_S$ multidirectional laminates at 75°C and 125°C using the principal moduli derived from the compliance curves with a quasi-elastic conversion. It was assumed that the time dependency of the fiber-dominated ply mechanical properties, longitudinal modulus E_{11} and Poisson's ratio ν_{12} , was negligible compared to the highly time-dependent matrix-dominated properties, transverse modulus $E_{22}(t)$ and in-plane shear modulus $G_{12}(t)$. The instantaneous elastic modulus E_{11} and Poisson's ratio ν_{12} were also assumed to be independent of temperature within the test range. The matrix-dominated transverse modulus $E_{22}(0)$ and shear modulus $G_{12}(0)$, on the other hand, vary with temperature as seen from the experimental data in Figure 4. Laminated plate theory was applied to calculate the longitudinal moduli $E_L(t)$ of the multidirectional laminates from the ply properties determined in the creep test. In these calculations the $[\pm 45]$ and $[90]$ plies in the multidirectional laminates are assumed to be under uniaxial stress (Poisson's effects are neglected), and $E_{22}(t)$ and $G_{12}(t)$ at 75°C and 125°C are assumed to be independent of the applied stress level within the test range. (The calculated uniaxial ply stresses range from 86 to 172 MPa for the $[\pm 45]$ plies and 17 to 29 MPa for the $[90]$ plies in the multidirectional laminates, whereas shear and transverse creep data were collected at 69.5 and 24.5 MPa, respectively, from the corresponding composites.) The total longitudinal strain for the multidirectional laminate is calculated from the time-dependent modulus $E_L(t)$ and the creep stress; subtraction of the instant strain at the test temperature from this value gives the longitudinal creep strain for the laminate. These calculated creep strains are compared with measured creep strains in Table 3.

TABLE 3. Comparison of Experimental and Predicted Creep of Multidirectional Laminates

Laminate	Creep Stress (MPa)	Creep Time (min)	Creep Strain, 10^{-6}			
			At 75°C		At 125°C	
			Prediction	Experiment	Prediction	Experiment
$[45/90_2/-45]_S$	52	100	48	47	-	-
		1080	62	65	-	-
	103	100	-	-	124	135
		1080	-	-	209	198
$[45/0/-45/90]_S$	207	100	30	45	38	58
		1080	40	55	68	73

Both predicted and measured strains are remarkably small for the conditions under which the tests were done. In almost all cases the predictions slightly underestimate the measured creep strains. Considering the assumptions made in this simple analytical approach, however, there is fairly good agreement between experiment and prediction, with the largest discrepancy being 20 microstrain. Further validation is necessary by conducting creep tests at higher temperatures (at which creep strains will be higher and any discrepancies between experiment and prediction will be magnified) and at different stress levels.

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSIONS

The creep behavior of the IM7/5250-4 composite system was investigated using short-term creep tests (100 min.) at various temperatures to determine the transverse and shear creep compliances ($S_{22}(t)$ and $S_{66}(t)$, respectively) and construct master curves to predict these quantities over longer periods of time. Using these results in conjunction with laminated plate theory, an attempt was made to calculate time-dependent Young's moduli, $E_L(t)$, of multidirectional laminates and thereby predict their creep behavior. Two laminate orientations selected for this study were $[45/90_2/-45]_S$ and $[45/0/-45/90]_S$. Measured creep strains at 75°C and 125°C compared well

with predictions, although values in both cases were lower than expected from tests on other materials. This may be due to the fact that the highest test temperature was at least 120°C lower than the material's glass transition temperature. Additional creep testing at higher temperatures and creep stresses is required for further validation of the analytical approach used to predict creep behavior.

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